

Condensation of 2-Anilino-4-methylquinoline Derivatives with Substituted-diethylmalonate and Studies of Isomerism through Nmr Spectra

N. D. SHARMA, SANTOSH KUMAR, P. V. BAKORE and B. C. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 6 February 1979, accepted 22 January 1987

2 [*N*-(2,2-Dicarbethoxyvinyl)anilino]-4-methyl-quinoline (6), 2-[*N*-(2,2-dicarbethoxyvinyl)-2-chloroanilino]-4-methylquinoline (7) and 2-*N*-(2,2-dicarbethoxyvinyl)-4-methylquinoline (8) were prepared by condensing ethoxymethylene diethyl malonate (4) with 2-anilino-4-methyl-quinoline (1), 2-(2-chloroanilino)-4-methylquinoline (2) and 2-(4-methoxyanilino)-4-methyl quinoline (3), respectively. 2-[*N*-(2-Carbethoxy-2-phenacetyl)anilino]-4-methylquinoline (9) and 2 [*N*-(2-carbethoxy-2-phenacetyl)-2-chloroanilino]-4-methylquinoline (10) were prepared by the condensation of phenyl-diethyl malonate (5) with 1 and 2, respectively. The structures of the compounds (6-10) were elucidated through elemental analyses and nmr spectral studies (Table 1). The nmr spectra also revealed keto-enol tautomerism in compounds 9 and 10, and that the enolic forms were present as *Z*-isomers only.

Results and Discussion

OWING to the reactivity of the proton attached to nitrogen atom in compounds 1-3, the condensation with 4 and 5 proceeded easily¹⁻³ by heating under reduced pressure.

A signal as singlet for one proton at δ 6.72 disappeared by the addition of D₂O, accounting for the presence of a hydroxyl group in compound 9⁴. The nmr spectrum of 9 recorded in D₂O also indicated that there was no shift in the signals of methyl and methylene protons of the carbethoxy group. But the singlet due to the protons of methyl group at position-4 of the quinoline ring (δ 2.95) shifted to a higher field (δ 2.75). Rotation at the -N-C= bond brings the hydroxyl group near the heterocyclic nitrogen, thereby possibly including O H · N bonding and giving greater stability to the molecule. This would also bring the signal of the C₄-methyl protons to a considerably lower field. D₂O shake would break the hydrogen bonding, shifting the signal of C₄-methyl protons to a higher field. This is only possible when 9 is in *Z*-enolic form and not *E*-enolic form.

It may be noted that compound 11 could not be isolated in pure form from the crude resinous mass obtained by the condensation of 3 with 5.

Keto-enol tautomerism in 9: The nmr spectrum of 9 revealed some additional signals of low intensity. These could be due either to the keto form or the *E*-enolic form. The possibility of *E*-enolic form could be ruled out by the absence of any additional signals of the OH proton. In the keto form of 9, the quartet of CH₂ protons and the singlet of the protons of the methyl group (at position-4 of the quinoline ring) should move

towards higher field in comparison with those of the *Z*-enolic form. On this basis, the small quartet at δ 3.50 and a singlet at δ 2.75 should be accountable for the carbethoxy group and the methyl group of position-4 of the quinoline ring, respectively, in the keto form of 9. From the relative intensity of the singlets, it was concluded that the keto-enol ratio in 9 was about 1 : 6. The greater stability of the enol form in comparison to the keto form could be explained on the basis of appearance of a double bond and hydrogen bonding which restrict the rotation, thereby obliterating collisions between bulkier groups.

When 9 and 10 were treated separately with aqueous ammonia in the cold, hydrolysis followed by decarboxylation occurred, resulting in compounds 12 and 13, respectively. Compounds 9 and 10 are slightly hygroscopic and have long range of melting point.

The comparison of the nmr spectra of 9 and 12 revealed that there was no signal for protons of a carbethoxy group in the nmr spectrum of 12. There appeared a new signal as a singlet for two protons at δ 4.2. The number of aromatic protons remained unchanged. On the basis of these observations, 12 was assigned the structure of 2-(*N*-phenylacetylanilino)-4-methylquinoline by similar reasons, 13 is 2-(*N*-phenacetyl-2-chloroanilino)-4-methylquinoline.

Easier decarbethoxylation of 9 and 10 as compared to the one of 6-8 could be due to the conversion of the enol form into keto form. This conversion would make the carbethoxy group more prone to decarbethoxylation, while in compounds 6-8, addition of a base would not result in such an easy decarbethoxylation. This is because of the fact that the carbethoxy groups are stabilised by the

TABLE 1—Nmr Spectra (δ ppm) of Compounds 4–13

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	OH or CH	Olefinic	Aromatic	OCH ₃	CH ₃ at position-4	—OH,—	—OH,
4	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	—	—	—	—	—	4.20(2H, q) 4.15(4H, q)	1.85(3H, t) 1.25(6H, t)
5	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₄	4.5(1H, s) (OH)	—	7.25(5H)	—	—	4.10(4H, q)	1.15(6H, t)
6	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	—	9.05(1H, s)	7.25–8.15(9H) 6.5(1H, s)	—	2.52(3H, s)	4.32(2H, q) 3.50(2H, q)	1.30(3H, t) 1.05(3H, t)
7	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	—	9.30(1H, s)	7.20–8.25(8H) 6.35(1H, s)	—	2.55(3H, s)	4.30(2H, q) 3.60(2H, q)	1.35(3H, t) 1.15(3H, t)
8	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	—	9.25(1H, s)	6.85–8.10(8H) 6.45(1H, s)	3.85(3H, s)	2.47(3H, s)	4.25(2H, q) 3.55(2H, q)	1.30(3H, t) 1.05(3H, t)
9	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ HCl	6.72(s) 0.85 H(OH)	—	7.20–8.20(14H) (including C ₂ –H) 9.00(1H, d, C ₂ –H)	—	2.75–2.95(3H, s)	3.50–4.32(2H, q)	1.30(3H, t)
10	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl HCl	6.7(s) 0.85H(OH)	—	7.25–8.25(18H) 9.05(1H, d)	—	2.75–2.95(3H, s)	4.32–4.60(2H, q)	1.25(3H, t)
12	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O	—	—	7.10–8.00(14H) 9.00(1H, d)	—	2.75(3H, s)	4.2(1H, s)	—
13	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ OCl	—	—	7.15–8.10(13H) 9.05(1H, d)	—	2.75(3H, s)	4.2(2H, s)	—

delocalisation of π -electrons of ethylenic bond and carboxy group.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60D using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was ascertained by tlc using silica gel G as adsorbent and ethanol–ethyl acetate–formic acid (80 : 10 : 10) as mobile phase.

2-[N-(2,2-Dicarbethoxyvinyl)anilino]-4-methylquinoline (6): A mixture of 2-anilino-4-methylquinoline (1, 4.68 g, 0.02 mol) and ethoxymethylene diethylmalonate (6.48 g, 0.03 mol) was heated under reduced pressure (25–30 mm) at 210–15° for 8 h. It was then cooled and triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The crude product was crystallised from acetone and petroleum ether to yield 6 (5.02 g, 61%), m.p. 131° (Found: C, 70.83; H, 5.62; N, 6.75. C₂₄H₂₄N₂O₄ calcd for: C, 71.28; H, 5.84; N, 6.93%).

Similarly, 2-[N-(2,2-dicarbethoxyvinyl)-2-chloroanilino]-4-methylquinoline (7) and 2-[N-(2,2-dicarbethoxyvinyl)-4-methoxyanilino]-4-methylquinoline (8) were obtained by condensing 4 with 2-(2-chloroanilino)-4-methylquinoline (2) and 2-(4-methoxyanilino)-4-methylquinoline (3), respectively: 7 (59.8%), m.p. 106–7° (Found: C, 65.50; H, 5.68; N, 6.43. C₂₄H₂₃O₄N₂Cl calcd. for C, 65.70; H, 5.60; N, 6.38%); 8 (61.5%), m.p. 140–1° (Found: C, 69.21; H, 6.21; N, 6.31. C₂₅H₂₆O₅N₂ calcd. for: C, 69.17; H, 5.99; N, 6.45%).

2-[N-(2-Carbethoxy-2-phenacetyl)-anilino]-4-methylquinoline (9): A mixture of 1 (4.68 g, 0.02 mol) and phenyldiethyl malonate (5; 6.08 g, 0.03 mol) was heated under reduced pressure (25–30 mm) at 210–15° for 11 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and triturated to a pasty mass. The whole content was poured into ice-water and extracted with solvent ether. The ether solution after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was distilled under reduced pressure when a thick red-brown oil was obtained, 9 HCl, (5.5 g, 58%); m.p. 100–10° (Found: C, 76.81; H, 5.68; N, 6.56. C₂₇H₂₄N₂O₄ calcd. for: C, 76.41; H, 5.61; N, 6.60%).

Similarly, 2-[N-(2-carbethoxy-2-phenacetyl)-2-chloroanilino]-4-methylquinoline (10, HCl) by the condensation of 2 with phenyldiethylmalonate (57.6%), m.p. 104–15° (Found: C, 70.43; H, 5.21; N, 6.34. C₂₇H₂₃O₄N₂Cl calcd. for: C, 70.66; H, 5.07; N, 6.16%).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Nitya Nand and Dr. C. M. Gupta, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for valuable suggestions.

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